

Concentration Effects on Equilibria in Pfeiffer Effect Systems of Fast-racemising Complexes†

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The equilibria in several Pfeiffer Effect systems, differing in concentrations and concentration ratios of complex to environment substance, were studied. It was found that keeping the complex concentration constant while increasing the concentration of the environment substance, results in an increase in the conversion of one enantiomer of the complex to the other, which supports the proposed hydrogen-bonding mechanism for the equilibrium displacement

The Pfeiffer Effect¹ is the change in optical rotation that occurs when a racemic mixture of an optically labile complex is placed into a solution of one enantiomer of an optically active compound (called the 'environment substance'). For example, if an aqueous solution *levo*-malic acid is added to a solution of a racemic mixture of an optically *stable* complex, such as $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ (en=ethylenediamine), no change in optical rotation is observed. However, if the same solution of malic acid is added to a racemic mixture of an optically *labile* complex, such as $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ (phen=*o*-phenanthroline), a marked change in optical rotation of the system is observed to occur, over a period of about 120 h. This change is known as the 'Pfeiffer Effect'.

Dwyer² and Kirschner³ attribute this change in rotation to a shift in the equilibrium between the *dextro* and *levo* enantiomers of the complex—a shift that occurs because of the presence of an optically active 'environment' (the *levo*-malic acid) around the complex. Kirschner and his coworkers⁴ have shown that a hydrogen bonding mechanism is responsible for this equilibrium shift, *levo*-malic acid (the *S* enantiomer) fits preferentially (over *R*-malic acid) into the Δ propeller formed by the *ortho*-phenanthroline ligands of the $(-)_D$ complex—via hydrogen bonding of the oxygen-containing protons of the malic acid to the π -electron clouds of the ligands. This insertion of the environment substance into the propeller blades formed by the ligands of one enantiomer of the complex inhibits the ability of that enantiomer to isomerise to the opposite enantiomer, thus altering the equilibrium between the enantiomers.

A question has arisen about whether the shift in the equilibrium (and in the equilibrium constant for this shift) can be changed by alteration of the

concentrations and/or concentration ratios of the complex to the environment substance. The equation initially proposed for the equilibrium shift is

$$\Delta(+)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+} = \Delta(-)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$$

and the equilibrium constant for this reaction is represented by the equation,

$$K = \{\Delta(-)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}\} / \{\Delta(+)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}\}$$

In this work, the authors prepared a series of Pfeiffer-active systems using *racemic*- $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ and *levo*-malic acid, which differ in concentrations of the complex and the environment substance, and which also differ in the ratio of complex to the environment substance. For each system the equilibrium shift was observed experimentally, and the equilibrium constant was calculated, based upon the optical rotations observed for the system and corrected for the presence of the optically active environment substance.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows how the equilibrium constants of hypothetical Pfeiffer systems are obtained—using a complex (initially racemic) having enantiomers that possess a molar rotation⁵, $[M]$, of $+74^\circ$ and -74° . It may be noted that a 50–50 mixture will show no optical rotation, while 100–0 mixture will show the molar optical rotation of one of the pure enantiomers. Also note that it is possible to determine the equilibrium constant of a system having any ratio of the *D* : *L* enantiomers from a determination of its molar optical rotation.

Table 2 shows the determination of equilibrium constants of one of the real systems employed in this study, in which the pure enantiomers of the $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ complex have molar optical rotations⁵ of $11,780^\circ$. It may be noted, for example, that if the

†The authors are pleased to dedicate this paper to four dear colleagues who have reached important milestones in their lives: Professor D. Banerjee, of the University of Calcutta, who is celebrating his sixtieth year, Professor Viktor Gutmann, of the Technische Universität Wien, and Professor João de Oliveira Cabral, of the University of Oporto, who are celebrating their seventieth year, and Professor Pedro Aymonino, who is celebrating his sixtieth year. The authors wish to congratulate them on their many important and significant achievements and to wish them many more years of productive activity.

TABLE 1—CALCULATION OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF A PFEIFFER-ACTIVE SYSTEM CONTAINING A HYPOTHETICAL COMPLEX, ONE ENANTIOMER OF WHICH HAS A MOLAR ROTATION OF +74°

Enantiomer concn.	Molar optical rotation (°)	Equilibrium constant	Multiplying factor*
100.00 D	74.00	0.0000	1.000
0.00 L			
99.00 D	72.52	0.0101	0.980
1.00 L			
98.00 D	71.04	0.0204	0.960
2.00 L			
51.00 D	1.48	0.9608	0.020
49.00 L			
50.10 D	0.15	0.9960	0.002
49.90 L			
50.00 D	0.00	1.0000	0.000
50.00 L			
49.90 D	-0.15	1.0040	-0.002
50.10 L			
49.00 D	-1.48	1.0408	-0.020
51.00 L			
2.00 D	-71.04	49.0000	-0.960
98.00 L			
1.00 D	-72.52	99.0000	-0.980
99.00 L			
0.00 D	-74.00	—	-1.000
100.00 L			

*Ref. 6.

 TABLE 2—CALCULATION OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF A PFEIFFER-ACTIVE SYSTEM CONTAINING THE REAL COMPLEX, [Ni(phen)₃]²⁺, ONE ENANTIOMER OF WHICH HAS A MOLAR ROTATION OF +11,780°*

Enantiomer concn.	Molar optical rotation (°)	Equilibrium constant	Multiplying factor**	Observed Pfeiffer rotation (°)
100.00 D	11,780	0.0000	1.000	
0.00 L				
99.00 D	11,540	0.0101	0.980	
1.00 L				
98.00 D	11,310	0.0204	0.960	
2.00 L				
52.00 D	471	0.9231	0.040	
48.00 L				
51.00 D	236	0.9608	0.020	
49.00 L				
50.10 D	23.6	0.9960	0.002	
49.90 L				
50.00 D	0.00	1.0000	0.000	
50.00 L				
49.90 D	-23.6	1.0040	-0.002	
50.10 L				
49.554 D	-105	1.0180	-0.0089	-0.210 ^a
50.446 L				
49.00 D	-236	1.0408	-0.020	
51.00 L				
2.00 D	-11,310	49.0000	-0.960	
98.00 L				
1.00 D	-11,540	99.0000	-0.980	
99.00 L				
0.00 D	-11,780	—	-1.000	
100.00 L				

*Complex concn.: 0.020 M; environment: *levo*-malic acid (concn., 0.040 M); solvent: water; wavelength: 589 nm; temp.: 21.1°. **Ref. 6.

^aThese are the actual, observed optical rotation and calculated equilibrium constant for this particular system. The observed Pfeiffer rotation is the maximum optical rotation observed during the appearance of the Pfeiffer Effect, corrected for the optical activity of the environment substance.

TABLE 3—EFFECTS OF CHANGES IN CONCENTRATIONS AND CONCENTRATION RATIOS OF COMPLEX TO ENVIRONMENT SUBSTANCE ON THE EQUILIBRIA OF A PFEIFFER EFFECT SYSTEM*

Enantiomer concn. (M) Complex : Envir.	Observed Pfeiffer rotation (°)	Equilibrium constant
0.020 : 0.040	-0.210	1.018
0.020 : 0.080	-0.465	1.040
0.040 : 0.020	-0.205	1.009
0.040 : 0.040	-0.434	1.019
0.040 : 0.080	-0.760	1.033
0.040 : 0.160	-1.579	1.069

*The equilibrium $\Delta(+)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+} = \Delta(-)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$; equilibrium constant: $K = \{\Delta(-)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}\} / \{\Delta(+)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}\}$; complex: Δ, Δ -[Ni(phen)₃]²⁺Cl₂; environment substance: S(-)D malic acid; wavelength; 589 nm; temp.: 21°.

molar rotation of a given mix of the D(Δ) and L(Δ) enantiomers of this complex is -105°, then the mix in question contains 49.554% D and 50.446% L enantiomers, and the equilibrium constant for that system is 1.0180 (representing about a 1% enrichment of the L enantiomer in this case). This is actually the case for this system, which contains a ratio of complex : environment substance of 1 : 2, i.e. the concentrations of the complex and environment substance are 0.02 and 0.04 M, respectively.

Determinations were carried out with the same complex and environment substance, but at different ratios and different concentrations of these substances, and the results are summarised in Table 3.

Conclusions :

As can be seen from Table 3, for the conversion of $\Delta(+)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ to $\Delta(-)_D[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ during the Pfeiffer Effect, as the concentrations of the complex are held constant and the concentrations of the environment substance are increased, the magnitude of the Pfeiffer Effect increases (i.e. there is a greater conversion of the $\Delta(+)$ enantiomer of to the $\Delta(-)$ enantiomer), resulting in an increase in the equilibrium constant for the $\Delta - \Delta$ shift. Also, as the concentrations of the environment substance are held constant and the concentrations of the complex are increased, the magnitude of the Pfeiffer Effect decreases (i.e. there is a smaller conversion of the $\Delta(+)$ enantiomer of to the $\Delta(-)$ enantiomer), resulting in a decrease in the equilibrium constant for the $\Delta - \Delta$ shift.

It can also be seen from Table 3 that increasing the concentration of both the complex and the environment substance, while keeping their ratio constant, increases the magnitude of the $\Delta - \Delta$ shift, as well as the equilibrium constant for this shift.

These observations support the proposed hydrogen-bonding mechanism⁴ for the equilibrium displacement, since increasing the concentration of environment molecules (while keeping the concentration of complex ions constant) would be expected to result in a larger number of the S-environment

molecules becoming hydrogen-bonded to the ligands comprising the Δ propeller configuration of the complex (the preferred configuration for attachment of the *S*-environment substance). This would further stabilise this configuration and inhibit its return to the opposite enantiomer during the occurrence of the dynamic equilibrium process, thereby increasing the equilibrium constant for the $\Delta - \Delta$ shift.

Obviously, since the magnitude of the equilibrium constant at a single temperature is affected by concentration changes (of the complex and/or the environment substance), then the equilibrium constant being measured is only a 'pseudo' equilibrium constant. This 'pseudo' constant is for the equation in which only the *dextro* and *levo* enantiomers of the complex are in equilibrium. The true equilibrium must be for a different system, and it is proposed that this system is one that involves both enantiomers of the complex as well as the environment substance. Work is currently underway to verify this proposal.

Experimental

The *racemic*-[Ni(phen)₃]Cl₂ was prepared and resolved according to the method of Kauffman and Takahashi⁷. Reagent grade *levo*-malic acid (Aldrich) was used as received. The Pfeiffer systems were

observed for optical activity using a Perkin-Elmer 241 photoelectric polarimeter. The concentrations and concentration ratios of complex and environment substance used are indicated in the tables.

References

1. P. PFEIFFER and K. QUEHL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2667; 1932, **65**, 560.
2. F. P. DWYER, E. C. GYARFAS and M. F. O'DWYER *Nature*, 1951, **167**, 1036.
3. S. KIRSCHNER and P. SERDIUK in "Stereochemistry of Optically Active Transition Metal Compounds" eds. K. SAITO and B. DOUGLAS, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, 1980, **119**, 239.
4. S. KIRSCHNER, N. AHMAD, C. MUNIR and R. POLLOCK, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1979, **51**, 913.
5. Molar rotation, $[M] = ([\alpha])(MW)/100 = \alpha_{\text{obs}} / \{[C](l_m)\}$, where $[\alpha]$ is specific optical rotation, MW the molecular weight of the complex, α_{obs} the observed optical rotation, $[C]$ the molar concentration of the complex, and l_m the path-length of the sample in meters, all at a given wavelength and temperature.
6. The Multiplying Factor for a mixture of enantiomers is the factor that, when multiplied by the absolute value of the molar optical rotation of a (pure) enantiomer of the complex, will give the molar optical rotation of the enantiomer-mix in question, i.e. M.F. = $\{[D] - [L]\} / \{[D] + [L]\}$, where $[D]$ and $[L]$ are the molar concentrations of the dextrorotatory and levorotatory enantiomers of the complex, respectively, in a given mixture of these isomers.
7. G. B. KAUFFMAN and L. T. TAKAHASHI, *Inorg Synth*, 1966, **8**, 227.